

CONSTRAINTS FACED BY POMEGRANATE GROWERS OF MAHARASHTRA IN ADOPTION OF RECOMMENDED CULTIVATION PRACTICES.**Ramesh Madhav Jadhav¹, Dr. Amit Kumar Mishra²,**

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*rameshjbitech@rediffmail.com**(MS Received: 24.01.2023; MS Revised:25.02.2023; MS Accepted: 26.03.2023)***MS 3007****(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE EXTENSION AND COMMUNICATION.)****Abstract: -**

The present study was conducted in Ahmednagar, Nashik and Solapur districts of Maharashtra state considering the larger area and production of pomegranate. Pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) commonly known as anar, dalim, matulum is an important fruit of tropical and subtropical regions of India. The wide adaptability, hardy nature, low maintenance cost, steady and high yields, fine table and therapeutic values, better keeping quality and possibilities to throw the plants into rest period when there is scarcity of irrigation water are some of the qualities which make this fruit crop ideally suitable for semi arid and arid regions. During the study, it was observed that the major constraints faced by pomegranate growers in study area were occurrence of oily spot disease, unavailability of labour, unavailability of crop insurance, timely unavailability of recommended fertilizers, occurrence of wilt disease, adverse climatic condition, fluctuation in market prices, regular updation of recent technology and unavailability of market.

Keywords: Pomegranate, Constraints, Maharashtra**Introduction:**

Agriculture sector is the backbone of the Indian economy. India is the second largest producer of fruit in the World after China. The major fruit growing states in India are Maharashtra, Tamilnadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Pomegranate (*Punica granatum L.*) commonly known as anar, dalim, matulum is an important fruit of tropical and subtropical regions of India. Maharashtra is leading fruit production state in India. Grape, Pomegranate, Banana, Citrus, Guava, and Custard Apple are major fruits crops in Maharashtra. In Maharashtra, pomegranate is commercially cultivated in Solapur, Sangli, Nasik, Ahmednagar, Pune, Dhule, Aurangabad, Satara, Osmanabad and Latur districts. Ganesh, Bhagwa, Arakta, Mridula and Super Bhagwa are the different varieties of pomegranates produced in Maharashtra. The total production of pomegranate of India in 2016-2017 is 2442 thousand MT under the area of 209 thousand ha. among them Maharashtra having 1578.04 thousand MT under the area of 136.75 thousand ha. (Anonymous, 2017). Pomegranate is most suitable fruit crop for India, but when we look to average yield of pomegranate; it stands very low as compared to other fruit crops. This is a challenging task for the scientists and the farmers.

Material and Methods:**Result and Discussion:****Constraints faced by pomegranate growers in adoption of recommended cultivation practices.**

Sr. No.	Constraints	N	%
1	Occurrence of oily spot disease	151	83.88
2	Unavailability of Labour	127	70.55
3	Unavailability of crop insurance	123	68.33
4	Timely unavailability of recommended fertilizers	114	63.33
5	Occurrence of wilt disease	112	62.22
6	Adverse climatic condition	110	61.11
7	Fluctuation in market prices	96	53.33
8	Regular updation of recent technology	60	33.33
9	Unavailability of market	57	31.66

In the constraints, majority of the respondents reported that, occurrence of oily spot disease (83.88 Per cent), unavailability of labour (70.55 Per cent), unavailability of crop insurance (68.33 Per cent), timely unavailability of recommended fertilizers (63.33 Per cent) were the major constraints.

Whereas, occurrence of wilt disease (62.22 per cent), adverse climatic condition (61.11 per cent), fluctuation in market prices (53.33 per cent), regular updation of recent technology (33.33 Per cent) and unavailability of market (31.33 per cent) constraints were also reported by majority of the pomegranate respondents.

Conclusion:

Nashik, Solapur and Ahmednagar are the major pomegranate producing districts in the Maharashtra. These three districts together accounted for more than 50.00% of area & production under pomegranate in the state. Hence, based on highest area and production in the Maharashtra, the Nashik, Solapur and Ahmednagar districts were selected for study.

The primary unit of the sample was talukas of these three districts. The leading talukas of pomegranate cultivation in Nashik districts were Satana & Malegaon, in Solapur were Sangola and Pandharpur while in Ahmednagar district, Sangamner and Rahata talukas were there. All six talukas were selected purposively. The secondary unit of the sample was villages. Three villages from each talukas having maximum area under pomegranate cultivation were selected for the study.

For the selection of pomegranate growers, the purposive sampling method was used. Ten pomegranate growers from the list of farmers growing pomegranate were randomly selected from each chosen village. Thus, a total of 180 pomegranate growers were selected and personal interviews with structured schedule was developed for the present study. Data were collected from primary sources to achieve the stated objectives.

Hence it can be concluded from the study that the major constraints faced by pomegranate growers in study area were occurrence of oily spot disease, unavailability of labour, unavailability of crop insurance, and timely unavailability of recommended fertilizers. It can also conclude that least felt constraints were occurrence of wilt disease, adverse climatic condition, fluctuation in market prices, regular updation of recent technology and unavailability of market. With the help of the above study the researcher tried to understand the related problems of pomegranate growers. Conclusions of this study will be helpful to pomegranate growers and agencies who are

engaged in production and marketing of pomegranate for designing future policies.

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